

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ACTIVITY ON CHEMICAL
CONSTITUTION. PART XLVIII. THE ROTATORY DISPERSION OF
METHYL, ETHYL, PHENYL, *o*-TOLYL, *p*-TOLYL, α -NAPHTHYL
AND β -NAPHTHYL *d*-CAMPHOR- β -SULPHONATES

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The rotatory dispersion of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, *o*- and *p*-tolyl, and α - and β -naphthyl-*d*-camphor- β -sulphonates has been studied in 7 solvents for 13 wave-lengths ($\lambda = 6708$ to $4358\text{\AA}$) in the visible region of the spectrum. All the above compounds exhibit simple rotatory dispersion which can be expressed by Drude's one-term equation. The 'characteristic' wave-lengths, λ_0 s, vary from 3442 to $2600\text{\AA}$ in different cases.

In this communication we have discussed the rotatory dispersion of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, α -naphthyl and β -naphthyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonates in seven solvents.

The rotatory dispersion of these compounds in all the seven solvents can be expressed by Drude's one-term equation, $[\alpha]_{\lambda} = K/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2$, where K is the rotation constant and λ_0^2 , the dispersion constant. It is therefore 'simple'.

Out of 627 observations, in as many as 475 the difference between the observed and calculated values of specific rotations corresponds to a deviation of 0.01° or less in the observed angle of rotation and in as many as 140, this deviation lies between 0.01° and 0.03° . In the remaining 12 cases, the difference is 0.04° or above for wave-lengths mostly in the blue region of the spectrum which are difficult to read.

The values of the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, λ_0 s, vary from 3442 to $2600\text{\AA}$.

It is observed that the alkyl esters generally possess a higher rotatory power than the aryl esters (Tables I to VII), with minor exceptions as in the case of ethyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate in benzene and acetone (Table A). Methyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate has a higher rotatory power than the corresponding ethyl derivative with minor variations (Tables I and II). *o*-Tolyl and α -naphthyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonates show higher specific rotations than their *para* and β -isomers respectively in all solvents (Tables IV to VII).

Position Isomerism and Rotatory Power

The specific rotatory powers, $[\alpha]_{5461}^{25}$, of the seven esters described above in seven solvents are recorded in Table A.

The effect of position isomerism on optical rotatory power could not be completely studied, as *m*-tolyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate was gummy in consistency and could not be isolated in a pure condition. It is, however, found that the *para* isomer has a lower rotatory power than the *ortho* isomer in all solvents. The sequence of the decreasing order of the rotatory powers is $o > un > p$ in chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methyl alcohol, whereas it is $un > o > p$ in benzene, pyridine and ethyl alcohol.

It does not therefore support Frankland's *lever-arm* hypothesis (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1896, 69, 284).

TABLE A

Specific rotatory powers of the ester for Hg₅₄₀₁ at 35° in different solvents.

Esters of <i>d</i> -camphor- β -sulphonic acid.	Benzene. *(2.28)	Chloroform. (5.2)	Ethyl acetate (6.11)	Pyridine. (12.4)	Acetone. (21.5)	EtOH. (25.8)	MeOH 31.5)
Methyl	64.00	55.00	60.00	52.50	55.00	49.00	48.00
Ethyl	59.50	56.00	60.50	53.00	49.00	45.00	45.50
Phenyl	64.50	47.00	53.50	50.50	49.50	43.00	40.50
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	59.00	48.00	54.50	47.50	50.00	41.00	41.00
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	57.50	43.50	45.50	41.50	39.00	40.10	32.50
α -Naphthyl	58.50	52.50	57.50	52.50	54.50	41.00	41.00
β -Naphthyl	55.50	45.50	48.50	43.50	41.00	40.00	36.00

* Figures in simple brackets indicate the dielectric constants of the solvents.

Influence of Solvent on Rotatory Power

It is found that the magnitude of the dielectric constants of the solvents and that of the rotatory power of these esters in solution in them run generally in the opposite direction with minor variations (Table A): the order of the decreasing rotatory power in different solvents is benzene (2.28)* > ethyl acetate (6.11) > chloroform (5.2) > pyridine (12.4) > ethyl alcohol (25.8) > methyl alcohol (31.5), except in the case of phenyl ester where the positions of pyridine and chloroform are interchanged. Acetone (21.5), however, behaves abnormally in almost half the cases investigated.

*The 'Characteristic' Wave-lengths, λ_{cs} , of the Esters of *d*-Camphor- β -sulphonic Acid in Different Solvents*

As already mentioned above, the values of the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, λ_{cs} , of the esters in different solvents vary from 3442 to 2600Å. These values, deduced from Tables I to VII, are shown in Table B.

* The figures in brackets are the dielectric constants of the solvents.

On examination of the structural formula of the esters,

it is found that there is only one chromophore, the keto group, $>\text{C}=\text{O}$, which has a 'characteristic' wave-length of about $2800\text{\AA}$ in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum.

A study of Table B reveals that the 'characteristic' wave-lengths corresponding to this value ($2800\text{\AA}$) are found only in a few cases, as indicated below (and shown underlined in Table B): Ethyl ester in chloroform ($2922\text{\AA}$) and ethyl acetate ($2917\text{\AA}$), phenyl ester in benzene ($2600\text{\AA}$), α -naphthyl ester in benzene ($2985\text{\AA}$), ethyl acetate ($2990\text{\AA}$) and pyridine ($2989\text{\AA}$) and β -naphthyl ester in benzene ($2896\text{\AA}$).

Thus out of 49 cases recorded above, only in 7 cases the 'characteristic' wave-lengths correspond to the ultraviolet absorption band of the ketonic group. In the remaining cases, λ_0 lies between 3442 and $3014\text{\AA}$.

TABLE B

The values of the characteristic wave-lengths of the esters in different solvents.

Esters of <i>d</i> -camphor- β -sulphonic acid.	Benzene.	CH_2Cl_2 .	Ethyl-acetate.	Pyridine.	Acetone.	EtOH .	MeOH .
Methyl	3123	3125	3116	3293	3195	3142	3198
Ethyl	3065	2922	<u>2917</u>	3442	3195	3318	3051
Phenyl	<u>2600</u>	3068	3135	3232	3066	3196	3258
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	3135	3231	3227	3266	3241	3178	3162
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	3014	3231	3252	3239	3345	3251	3124
α -Naphthyl	<u>2985</u>	3047	<u>2990</u>	<u>2989</u>	3302	3402	3162
β -Naphthyl	<u>2896</u>	3165	3057	3152	3113	3148	3113

TABLE I
Rotatory dispersion of methyl d-camphor- β -sulphonate (m.p. 61°) at 35°

Solvents:	Benzene	Chloroform	Ethyl acetate	Pyridine	Acetone	Ethyl alcohol	Methyl alcohol
Conc: g./100 c.c.)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	(2.28)	(5.2)	(6.17)	(12.4)	(21.5)	(25.8)	(31.5)
	$\frac{13.20}{\lambda^2 - 0.0932}$	$\frac{10.90}{\lambda^2 - 0.1021}$	$\frac{12.06}{\lambda^2 - 0.0972}$	$\frac{10.01}{\lambda^2 - 0.1084}$	$\frac{10.90}{\lambda^2 - 0.1021}$	$\frac{9.860}{\lambda^2 - 0.0987}$	$\frac{9.386}{\lambda^2 - 0.1023}$
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_{\lambda} \\ \lambda \end{array} \right\}$	3193	3195	3116	3293	3195	3142	3198
λ_{max} (Å)	o. c.						
Lines.	o. c.						
6708	37.00	31.33	34.50	34.32	31.00	28.50	27.50
6438	40.50	34.88	37.50	38.00	34.50	31.23	31.00
6102	47.00	40.31	44.00	43.80	40.50	36.00	34.00
5893	52.00	44.44	48.50	48.23	45.00	40.50	38.50
5780	55.00	46.98	51.00	50.83	47.00	41.89	40.50
5468	64.00	55.35	59.50	59.75	55.00	49.50	48.00
5461	64.00	55.58	60.00	60.00	55.58	49.00	48.00
5209	73.00	64.43	69.00	69.28	64.50	57.12	55.52
5086	80.00	79.67	74.00	74.52	70.00	61.63	60.00
4800	94.50	95.26	89.50	90.18	84.50	74.42	72.50
4678	104.50	104.30	99.50	99.10	93.50	81.04	80.50
4603	110.00	117.60	105.00	105.20	99.00	88.50	86.00
4358	136.50	135.50	124.00	124.00	124.00	108.00	107.00

Figures in brackets in this and the following tables give the dielectric constants of the solvents.

TABLE II

Rotatory dispersion of ethyl d-camphor- β -sulphonate (m.p. 47°) at 35°

Solvents:	Benzene (2.28)	Chloroform (5.2)	Ethyl acetate (6.11)	Pyridine (12.4)	Acetone (21.5)	Ethyl alcohol (25.8)	Methyl alcohol (31.5)
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Calc.	$[\alpha]_D^{35}$	12.25	11.92	9.529	9.599	8.504	9.47
	$\lambda \frac{[\alpha]_D^{35}}{\lambda^2 - 0.0939}$	11.92	$\frac{12.85}{\lambda^2 - 0.0851}$	$\frac{9.529}{\lambda^2 - 0.1184}$	$\frac{9.599}{\lambda^2 - 0.1021}$	$\frac{8.504}{\lambda^2 - 0.1101}$	$\frac{9.47}{\lambda^2 - 0.0931}$
	$\lambda_0(\lambda)$ 3065	2922	2917	3442	3195	3318	3051
Lines.	0. c.	0. c.	0. c.	0. c.	0 c.	0. c.	0. c.
6798	35.00	32.50	35.50	28.50	28.00	25.00	26.00
6438	38.50	36.00	39.00	32.00	30.50	27.00	29.00
6104	43.50	42.00	44.50	37.50	35.50	32.50	33.50
5893	48.50	45.50	49.00	41.50	40.00	36.00	37.00
5780	51.00	48.00	51.00	45.00	41.50	38.00	39.00
5468	59.50	55.80	59.50	52.50	48.50	44.50	45.50
5461	59.50	56.00	60.50	53.00	49.00	45.00	45.84
5280	69.50	64.12	68.99	62.50	56.00	53.00	53.00
5086	74.00	68.00	73.50	68.50	61.50	58.00	56.81
4800	89.00	82.21	89.00	85.00	74.50	71.00	68.41
4678	98.50	89.50	96.00	94.50	83.00	77.50	75.00
4603	103.50	94.50	101.50	...	87.50	83.00	79.50
4358	127.50	114.00	122.50	...	109.00	106.50	97.00

TABLE III
Rotatory dispersion of phenyl d-*emphor*- β -sulphonate (m.p. 38°) at 35°.

Lines.	Benzene (2.28)		Chloroform (5.2)		Ethyl acetate (6.11)		Pyridine (12.4)		Acetone (21.5)		Ethyl alcohol (25.8)		Methyl alcohol (31.5)	
	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$	$o.$	$c.$
6708	39.50	39.38	26.50	26.95	30.50	30.60	29.00	28.31	28.50	28.31	24.00	24.01	22.00	22.43
6438	44.00	43.41	29.50	29.93	34.00	34.00	31.00	31.55	32.00	31.46	26.50	26.73	25.00	25.02
6104	49.00	49.39	35.00	34.45	39.50	39.14	36.50	36.50	36.00	36.19	31.00	30.88	29.00	29.01
5893	53.50	53.86	38.00	37.89	42.50	43.07	40.00	39.57	39.50	39.81	33.50	34.07	32.00	32.00
5780	56.50	56.50	40.00	39.97	45.50	45.50	42.50	42.60	42.00	42.00	36.00	36.00	34.00	33.84
5469	64.50	65.08	47.00	46.81	53.50	53.23	50.00	50.49	49.50	49.17	42.50	42.41	39.50	40.00
5461	64.50	65.31	47.00	47.00	53.50	53.44	50.50	50.50	49.50	49.36	43.00	42.59	40.50	40.17
5209	74.00	73.93	54.00	54.12	61.00	61.59	59.00	58.65	57.00	56.85	49.00	49.36	47.00	46.17
5086	79.00	78.81	58.00	58.27	67.00	66.32	64.00	63.44	61.50	61.48	52.50	52.32	50.00	50.56
4800	93.00	92.51	70.50	70.37	80.50	80.16	77.50	77.70	73.50	73.90	65.50	65.09	62.00	62.08
4678	98.00	98.37	76.50	76.85	85.50	85.90	86.00	85.51	80.00	80.70	72.00	71.50	69.00	68.40
4603	104.00	104.40	81.00	81.49	92.50	92.50	...	...	86.00	85.57	76.00	76.13	73.00	73.00
4358	123.00	123.00	100.00	100.00	114.00	114.00	...	...	105.00	105.00	95.00	95.00	91.50	91.97

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
 $[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35}$...
 Calc. ...

λ_0 (Å) ...

$o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$ $o.$ $c.$

$\frac{15.06}{\lambda^2 - 0.0675}$ $\frac{9.591}{\lambda^2 - 0.0941}$ $\frac{10.87}{\lambda^2 - 0.0984}$ $\frac{9.782}{\lambda^2 - 0.1045}$ $\frac{10.08}{\lambda^2 - 0.0940}$ $\frac{8.351}{\lambda^2 - 0.1021}$ $\frac{7.716}{\lambda^2 - 0.1061}$

2600 3058 3135 3232 3066 3196 3258

TABLE IV

Rotatory dispersion of o-tolyl d-camphor-β-sulphonate (m.p. 58°) at 35°.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Benzene (2.29)		Chloroform (5.2)		Ethyl acetate (6.11)		Pyridine (12.4)		Acetone (21.5)		Ethyl alcohol (25.8)		Methyl alcohol (31.5)	
	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35}$	$\frac{11.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.0984}$	1.00	$\frac{9.352}{\lambda^2 - 0.1043}$	1.00	$\frac{10.57}{\lambda^2 - .1035}$	1.00	$\frac{9.098}{\lambda^2 - 0.1067}$	1.00	$\frac{9.438}{\lambda^2 - 0.1050}$	1.00	$\frac{8.150}{\lambda^2 - 0.1009}$	1.00	$\frac{8.050}{\lambda^2 - 0.1000}$
Calc.	$\lambda, (\text{Å})$	3135	3231	3217	3266	3241	3178	3178	3178	3178	3178	3178	3178	3178
Lines.	α	c	α	c	α	c	α	c	α	c	α	c	α	c
6708	35.00	32.9	27.01	27.1	31.00	30.5	26.50	26.51	27.00	27.36	23.00	23.38	23.00	23.00
6438	37.00	36.6	30.00	30.2	34.00	34.0	30.00	29.57	30.50	30.50	25.50	25.99	25.0	25.61
6104	42.50	43.2	34.50	34.9	40.00	39.3	34.00	34.28	35.00	35.29	30.00	30.00	30.00	29.54
5893	46.50	46.5	38.50	38.5	44.00	43.4	38.0	37.84	35.50	38.97	33.50	33.99	32.00	32.56
5700	50.00	49.1	41.00	40.7	47.00	45.9	40.00	40.01	41.50	41.20	35.50	34.94	35.00	34.39
5468	59.00	57.7	48.00	48.0	54.50	54.1	47.50	47.32	48.50	48.65	41.50	41.30	40.50	40.44
5461	59.00	57.1	48.00	48.2	54.50	54.3	47.50	47.52	50.00	48.85	41.00	41.44	41.00	40.62
5209	67.00	66.9	56.00	56.0	63.00	63.0	55.50	55.21	56.00	56.75	47.50	47.83	47.00	46.89
5086	73.50	72.2	60.00	60.6	67.50	68.1	60.50	59.87	60.00	61.45	52.50	51.65	49.50	51.71
4800	87.00	87.3	74.50	73.9	82.00	83.0	74.50	73.77	74.50	74.98	62.00	62.70	62.00	61.52
4678	96.00	96.0	82.00	81.6	92.00	91.7	81.50	81.10	85.00	82.87	69.00	69.07	67.00	67.69
4603	101.50	102.1	89.50	87.5	96.00	97.6	86.50	86.18	87.50	88.37	73.50	73.50	72.00	72.00
4358	124.00	126.3	110.50	109.1	120.5	122.2	...	...	111.00	110.00	91.00	91.58	89.00	89.45

TABLE V

Rotatory dispersion of *p*-tolyl *D*-camphor- β -sulphonate (m.p. 64°) at 35°

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Benzene (2.28)	Chloroform (5.7)	Ethyl acetate (6.11)	Pyridine (12.4)	Acetone (21.5)	Ethyl alcohol (25.8)	Methyl alcohol (31.5)
Calc. {	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35}$	$\frac{8.377}{\lambda^3 - 0.1044}$	$\frac{9.068}{\lambda^3 - 0.0993}$	$\frac{8.082}{\lambda^3 - 0.1049}$	$\frac{7.264}{\lambda^3 - 0.1119}$	$\frac{87.661}{\lambda^3 - 0.1054}$	$\frac{6.623}{\lambda^3 - 0.0976}$
	$(\lambda_1(\beta)) \dots 3014$	3231	3152	3239	3345	3251	3124
Lines.	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>	<i>o.</i>
6708	33.50	24.00	25.86	24.09	22.01	22.50	18.50
6438	37.50	27.00	28.77	25.50	25.91	24.00	21.50
6101	42.50	31.23	33.18	30.50	29.97	29.50	24.00
5893	47.00	34.50	36.58	32.50	31.11	31.00	26.00
5782	49.00	36.47	38.50	35.00	32.59	32.50	28.00
5468	57.00	43.00	45.41	41.00	38.50	40.00	32.50
5461	57.50	43.40	45.59	41.50	39.00	42.00	32.50
5209	66.00	50.19	52.72	48.00	45.57	46.00	38.50
5086	71.00	54.29	56.89	52.50	49.55	50.00	41.50
4800	86.00	66.22	69.43	64.00	61.04	60.50	49.50
4678	94.00	73.50	75.82	71.00	67.50	67.50	54.00
4603	99.00	78.00	80.60	...	72.00	72.00	58.00
4358	120.50	98.05	100.00	...	93.00	91.00	72.00

TABLE VI

Rotatory dispersion of α -naphthyl d-camphor- β -sulphonate (m.p. 115°) at 35°.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Benzene (2.28)		Chloroform (5.2)		Ethyl acetate (6.11)		Pyridine (12.4)		Acetone (21.5)		Ethyl alcohol (25.8)		Methyl alcohol (31.5)	
	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00
Calc.	$\frac{12.27}{\lambda^2 - 0.0891}$		$\frac{10.77}{\lambda^2 - 0.0928}$		$\frac{11.97}{\lambda^2 - 0.0898}$		$\frac{10.95}{\lambda^2 - 0.0894}$		$\frac{10.28}{\lambda^2 - 0.1097}$		$\frac{7.473}{\lambda^2 - 0.1138}$		$\frac{8.154}{\lambda^2 - 0.1004}$	
	2985		3047		2990		2989		3302		3402		3163	
Lines.	0.	c.	0.	c.	0.	c.	0.	c.	0.	c.	0.	c.	0.	c.
6708	34.00	34.00	30.00	30.16	34.00	33.24	31.00	30.45	30.00	32.14	22.00	21.69	23.50	23.31
6438	38.00	37.70	33.50	33.38	36.50	36.89	34.00	33.69	33.50	33.64	25.00	25.02	26.00	25.93
6104	43.00	43.33	38.50	38.50	42.00	42.35	38.00	38.68	39.00	39.00	29.00	29.14	30.00	29.93
5893	48.00	47.53	42.50	42.35	46.50	46.50	42.50	42.48	43.50	43.14	32.50	32.29	33.00	33.00
5780	50.50	50.07	45.00	44.65	49.00	49.00	44.50	44.76	46.00	45.65	34.00	34.23	34.00	34.85
5468	58.50	58.45	52.50	52.24	57.50	57.23	52.50	52.25	54.00	54.09	41.00	40.79	41.00	41.02
5461	58.50	58.68	52.50	52.44	57.50	57.40	52.50	52.47	54.50	54.31	41.00	40.98	41.00	41.18
5209	67.50	67.33	60.00	60.36	65.50	65.95	60.50	60.22	61.00	63.33	47.50	48.06	47.50	47.62
5086	72.50	72.33	65.50	64.92	70.50	70.86	64.50	64.69	68.50	68.64	52.00	52.30	51.00	51.40
4800	85.50	86.54	79.00	78.00	85.60	84.84	77.50	77.41	84.50	84.33	65.00	65.07	62.50	62.36
4678	94.50	94.50	86.00	85.43	92.50	92.72	85.00	84.57	92.50	93.50	72.00	72.49	68.00	68.63
4663	100.00	100.00	90.50	90.50	98.00	98.11	87.00	89.52	100.00	100.00	78.00	77.84	73.00	73.03
4358	121.00	121.60	113.00	110.90	120.50	119.50	...	...	125.00	126.90	100.0	100.7	90.50	90.69

TABLE VII

Rotatory dispersion of β -naphthyl d-camphor- β -sulphonate (m.p. 100°) at 35

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Benzene (2.28)	Chloroform (5.2)	Ethyl acetate (6.11)	Pyridine (12.4)	Acetone (21.5)	Ethyl alcohol (25.8)	Methyl alcohol (31.5)
[α] _D ³⁵ ...	11.83	9.017	9.786	8.668	8.265	7.870	7.168
	$\lambda^3 - 0.0839$	$\lambda^3 - 0.1002$	$\lambda^3 - 0.0935$	$\lambda^3 - 0.0993$	$\lambda^3 - 0.0969$	$\lambda^3 - 0.0991$	$\lambda^3 - 0.0969$
Calc. {	2896	3165	3057	3152	3113	3148	3113
Lines.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.	o. c.
6708	32.50	26.00	27.50	25.00	23.00	22.00	20.00
6438	36.50	28.50	30.50	27.50	25.50	24.50	23.00
6104	41.00	31.00	35.50	32.00	30.00	29.00	26.00
5893	44.50	36.50	39.00	35.00	33.00	32.00	28.50
5780	48.00	38.50	41.00	37.00	35.00	33.50	30.00
5468	55.00	45.00	48.00	43.00	40.9	39.50	36.00
5461	55.50	45.50	47.7	43.50	41.00	40.00	36.00
5209	63.00	52.00	55.00	49.50	47.00	46.00	40.00
5086	69.00	56.00	59.2	54.00	51.00	49.00	44.00
4800	82.00	69.00	71.2	66.50	61.7	59.50	54.00
4678	87.50	76.00	78.00	72.50	67.8	66.00	59.00
4603	92.50	81.50	82.7	78.50	72.0	70.00	64.50
4358	112.50	100.00	103.00	90.00	89.0	86.50	77.00

Our results on the determination of the ultraviolet absorption maxima, $\lambda_{\max}$, of these esters (unpublished work) provide values of $\lambda_{\max}$ ranging from 2890 to 2600 Å. It is therefore not clear to what absorption bands the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_s) ranging between 3442 and 3014 Å (Table B) correspond. They do not agree with the value of $\lambda_{\max}$, as found by us. The elucidation of this discrepancy is still awaited. Its solution will throw light on the validity of Drude's equation, $[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \sum K/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2$, in which λ_0 s are the ultraviolet absorption bands controlling rotation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The esters will be described by us in a separate communication.

The rotatory dispersion measurements were carried out in a 2-dcm jacketed tube at 35° in seven solvents for 13 wave-lengths in the visible part of the spectrum ($\lambda=6708$ to 4358 Å). The values of λ_0 s, calculated from the dispersion formulae, are shown in Tables I to VII.

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